

The Effectiveness of the CO-OP Method in Rehabilitating Activities of Daily Living in a Patient With Parkinson's Disease: A Case Study

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Abstract

Introduction: Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neurological syndrome characterized by progressive deterioration of motor and cognitive functions, with a substantial impact on participation in activities of daily living. A key issue for occupational therapy in these patients is occupational performance, understood as the ability to carry out meaningful everyday tasks.

Methods: The person-centred CO-OP (Cognitive Orientation to daily Occupational Performance) approach, based on cognitive strategies, aims to improve occupational performance through a structured methodology focused on individualized functional goals and problem solving. This article presents a case study assessing the effectiveness of the CO-OP method in a 54-year-old patient compatible with an intermediate stage of PD according to the Hoehn and Yahr scale [1].

Results: The CO-OP-based intervention yielded positive outcomes by fostering strategic awareness, operational autonomy, and occupational satisfaction.

Conclusions: These data support the validity of this evidence-based model in occupational therapy for Parkinson's disease.

Keywords: Parkinson's disease; Occupational Therapy; CO-OP method; Occupational performance; Rehabilitation.

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INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder affecting about 1% of people over 60 years of age, with a significant impact on motor and non-motor functions [1-3]. A recent systematic review also identified intrinsic factors (e.g., individual vulnerabilities) and extrinsic factors, including dopaminergic therapy, as predispositions to impulse-control disorders in these patients. The authors stress that, to date, this is a predisposition rather than a causal link; hence the importance of thorough behavioural assessment within rehabilitation to improve patients' quality of life (QoL) [4]. In addition to cardinal symptoms—bradykinesia/freezing of gait, resting tremor, and rigidity—patients experience increasing limitations in basic activities of daily living (ADL) and instrumental activities of daily living (IADL), leading to reduced social participation and emotional well-being [5,6]. Recent literature has highlighted the increasing relevance of non-motor symptoms (NMS) in PD, which significantly affect functional autonomy and QoL. Among these, alexithymia—defined as a reduced ability to identify, describe, and regulate emotions—has been found to be highly prevalent in people with PD and is closely linked to deficits in executive functioning and emotional regulation, contributing to poorer psychosocial adjustment and lower QoL [7]. Furthermore, REM Sleep Behavior Disorder (RBD) is now recognized as a prodromal marker of cognitive decline in PD. RBD has been associated with impairments in executive functions, visuospatial skills, attention, and episodic memory, and it represents a significant predictor of mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and dementia in this population [8]. Additionally, dopaminergic therapy, while remaining the cornerstone of symptom management in PD, has been shown to modulate higher-order cognitive and emotional processes. Recent findings suggest that dopamine replacement therapy and dopamine agonists can enhance divergent thinking and creative expression in predisposed individuals by affecting reward-related circuits and executive flexibility, although these effects are not consistent across patients [9].

These insights underline the need for rehabilitation models that address not only motor impairments but also emotional, cognitive, and behavioural domains to improve functional outcomes and overall QoL in PD.

With respect to well-being and QoL, a recent exploratory study in early-stage PD examined correlations between patients' clinical and psychological factors (cognitive functions, anxiety, quality of life) and caregiver burden and perceived stress, measured with standardized questionnaires (CBI, FSQ, HRS-A). Results showed that patients' cognitive impairment (MoCA) correlated negatively with quality of life (PDQ-Cogn; $r = -0.48$, $p = 0.04$), whereas caregiver anxiety correlated positively with both physical stress ($r = 0.65$, $p = 0.003$) and emotional stress ($r = 0.57$, $p = 0.01$), along with greater family stress [10].

Occupational Therapy (OT) plays a central role in mitigating these limitations by promoting autonomy and QoL through individualized interventions on meaningful occupations [11,12]. Among evidence-based approaches in occupational practice, the Cognitive Orientation to daily Occupational Performance (CO-OP) stands out for its emphasis on cognitive and metacognitive strategies that guide the patient in solving functional problems via the Goal–Plan–Do–Check cycle [13].

Specifically, CO-OP is a client-centred therapeutic approach grounded in principles of cognitive and motor learning and aimed at improving occupational performance in individuals with functional difficulties. The model revolves around the metacognitive strategy “Goal–Plan–Do–Check,” which promotes self-regulation and problem solving through verbal guidance and guided discovery. The intervention is structured to facilitate acquisition of specific skills while fostering generalization and transfer across contexts. Empirical evidence from randomized controlled trials has demonstrated CO-OP’s effectiveness in improving participation and self-efficacy in paediatric populations (e.g., developmental coordination disorder) and adults (e.g., stroke, traumatic brain injury, Parkinson’s disease). The approach is characterized by flexibility, emphasis on patient autonomy, and integration of personally meaningful goals, making it an innovative and adaptable model in contemporary rehabilitation.

Although initially developed for children, CO-OP has shown promising results in adult neurological populations [14], offering interesting prospects for people with PD. Recent evidence suggests that CO-OP is a promising rehabilitation approach for patients with Parkinson’s disease, particularly for enhancing occupational performance and functional autonomy. Based on cognitive strategies and verbal guidance, the CO-OP model enables patients to develop metacognitive skills through the “Goal–Plan–Do–Check” sequence, facilitating adaptation to the motor and cognitive limitations typical of the disease. The intervention helps compensate for motor symptoms (e.g., bradykinesia, rigidity) through strategic action planning and addresses non-motor symptoms, such as reduced initiative and self-efficacy, by actively engaging patients in defining and achieving personal goals. Moreover, CO-OP promotes generalization of learned strategies to everyday contexts, helping maintain independence and QoL. Preliminary studies indicate that integrating CO-OP into multidisciplinary rehabilitation programs can support symptom management in PD, with positive effects on participation and motivation.

The most recent literature highlights that client-centred OT interventions grounded in meaningful activities and cognitive strategies can improve participation and reduce disease impact [15,16]. However, evidence on the structured application of CO-OP in people with Parkinson’s remains limited and fragmented. Alongside this model, cognitive rehabilitation through virtual reality has also shown promising results. In two randomized clinical trials by Maggio et al. [17-19], the role of virtual reality—both semi-immersive with the BTS Nirvana system and via smartphone-based telerehabilitation apps—was explored for cognitive rehabilitation in PD. The first trial (2018) showed significant improvements in executive and visuospatial abilities in the experimental group compared with the control group receiving traditional training. The second (2024) found that app-based rehabilitation fostered gains in cognitive, social, and affective domains (including theory of mind), with enhancement of executive functions and social cognition versus controls. Most CO-OP studies involve paediatric populations or adults with acquired brain injury; research specifically in PD is still exploratory. For example, the Fondazione Grigioni per il Morbo di Parkinson has published articles noting growing interest in cognitive and occupational approaches, but without systematic validation of the CO-OP protocol in this population [12,20]. Similarly, the Comitato Italiano Parkinson has emphasized the need for personalized rehabilitation, yet available scientific publications do not include randomized clinical trials comparing CO-OP with other rehabilitation models [21]. This gap underscores the urgency of controlled studies investigating CO-OP’s impact on motor and non-motor PD symptoms, QoL, and occupational participation. Given this background, the aim of the present work is to describe the effectiveness of a CO-OP intervention in an adult with PD, analyzing changes in occupational performance, perceived satisfaction, and quality of life. This contribution seeks to:

1. demonstrate the transferability of the CO-OP model to neurodegenerative contexts;
2. document the approach’s impact on meaningful daily activities;
3. offer operational guidance for integrating cognitive strategies into OT pathways for people with PD.

Through analysis of clinical outcomes and critical discussion of limitations, this work aims to help bridge the knowledge gap on CO-OP in PD and to provide insights for future controlled and interdisciplinary research.

METHODS

In this case study, the CO-OP approach was used to assess the intervention's effectiveness in terms of occupational autonomy, perceived satisfaction, and QoL. CO-OP is a client-centred rehabilitation approach structured around meaningful functional goals and based on cognitive and metacognitive strategies to facilitate acquisition of practical skills. Table 1 reports the treatment goals at T0.

Table 1. Treatment goals.

	<i>Goal</i>
<i>O1</i>	To analyse the effectiveness of the CO-OP approach in the rehabilitation of a patient with Parkinson's disease, with particular attention to improvements in occupational performance.
<i>O2</i>	To promote functional autonomy and increase the patient's subjective satisfaction in performing meaningful daily activities.
<i>O3</i>	To activate and strengthen cognitive and metacognitive strategies through the "Goal-Plan-Do-Check" cycle, in order to promote awareness, motivation, and personal initiative.
<i>O4</i>	To explore the transferability and adaptability of the CO-OP model to adults with degenerative neurological conditions, extending its application beyond the paediatric and post-stroke settings in which it is traditionally used.

The intervention was delivered in an outpatient setting, semi-structured and free of distractions, suitable for concentration and active patient participation. The therapeutic pathway comprised ten individual sessions of approximately 60 minutes each, over a total of five weeks at twice-weekly frequency. In the initial phase, the patient was cooperative; a history-taking interview was conducted along with an initial assessment of functioning in terms of fine and gross motor skills, eye-hand coordination, and bimanual coordination, with particular focus on how these abilities translated into participation in activities and the maintenance of autonomy in daily living.

The patient then independently identified three meaningful daily activities as priority goals: cutting meat, screwing/unscrewing, and using technological devices. Selection occurred through an initial interview focused on the personal meaning and functional importance of each activity in everyday life. Cutting meat was chosen for its relevance during meals and the difficulties encountered in handling kitchen utensils, particularly due to bradykinesia and reduced grip strength. Screwing tasks were selected for their practical value in household and maintenance activities and for the challenges related to bimanual coordination and fine dexterity. Finally, the use of technological devices (e.g.,

smartphone and tablet) was identified to improve communication, autonomy, and social participation, in response to cognitive and motor difficulties that hinder interaction with digital interfaces.

These activities formed the basis of the therapeutic intervention, which followed the CO-OP protocol centred on the metacognitive Goal–Plan–Do–Check cycle. This cycle was introduced gradually and reinforced through guided-discovery techniques that promoted the development of strategic awareness and self-efficacy in task management. Effectiveness was assessed using the COPM and PDQ-39 administered before treatment and after the ten sessions, allowing quantitative comparison of outcomes.

Instruments

The instruments used for assessment were the ADL (Activities of Daily Living) scale and the IADL (Instrumental Activities of Daily Living) scale, following interview and neuropsychological evaluation, to measure functional independence; and the Canadian Occupational Performance Measure (COPM) to capture perceived performance and satisfaction. The ADL and IADL are commonly used in geriatric and rehabilitation settings and have good content validity. For the ADL scale, the scalability coefficient ranges from 0.74 to 0.88, with high internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.94$) in post-stroke samples [22]. For the IADL scale, internal consistency is excellent ($\alpha = 0.94$), with factor loadings between 0.67 and 0.90. Factor analyses confirm a robust structure (CFI ≥ 0.98 ; RMSEA ≤ 0.08) and convergent validity with other functional measures [23]. The COPM is a semi-structured interview that identifies and evaluates personally meaningful activities in the domains of self-care, productivity, and leisure. For each priority activity, the individual rates performance and satisfaction on a 1–10 scale. The instrument shows good test–retest reliability (intraclass correlation coefficient, ICC ≈ 0.67 – 0.81), acceptable internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.73$ – 0.83 across samples), and good sensitivity to change (Minimal Important Change between 1.75 and 3.00 points) [24–26].

RESULTS

At the end of the CO-OP-based rehabilitation pathway, the patient showed significant improvements across the domains assessed, both subjectively and through standardized instruments. On the COPM, there was an increase in performance and satisfaction scores for all three target occupations—cutting food (including meat), screwing, and using technological devices—with clinically meaningful gains between baseline and post-intervention (Figure A1).

Figure A1. Comparison of performance and satisfaction at T0 and T1.

Performance scores improved from 3.6 (pre-intervention) to 7.2 (post-intervention), for a gain of +3.6 points. Satisfaction improved from 2.8 to 8.0, for a gain of +5.2 points. PDQ-39 results also indicated improvements in quality of life, with the greatest changes in mobility, activities of daily living, and emotional well-being (Figure A2).

Figure A2. Comparison of performance and satisfaction in the target instrumental activities.

Analysis of data from baseline (T0) to post-treatment (T1) showed significant improvement in both occupational performance and perceived satisfaction for the three chosen activities: cutting meat, screwing, and using technological devices. Cutting meat showed the greatest increase, with performance rising from 3 to 10 and satisfaction from 0 to 10, indicating not only acquisition of motor skills but also a strong impact on subjective well-being. Screwing tasks also improved substantially (from 3 to 9 in performance and from 1 to 9 in satisfaction), suggesting that cognitive strategies were effective in overcoming coordination and fine-dexterity difficulties. Although gains in the use of technological devices were more modest (from 3 to 6 for both performance and satisfaction), they still represented meaningful functional progress, likely constrained by greater cognitive complexity.

The patient reported reduced frustration, greater personal control over activities, and a gradual return to social participation. During sessions, increasing active engagement was observed, together with improved initiative, personal organization, and reflective capacity. The patient demonstrated an ability to generalize the Goal–Plan–Do–Check cycle to activities not directly addressed during therapy, indicating effective internalization of the method.

DISCUSSION

This case study shows that applying the CO-OP model in an adult with Parkinson's disease can lead to significant improvements in both occupational performance and subjective satisfaction. The results confirm that the CO-OP approach, originally developed for developmental disorders in childhood [27], can be effectively adapted to neurodegenerative rehabilitation settings, consistent with findings from two prior studies [5,14]. The patient benefited clearly from adopting the Goal–Plan–Do–Check metacognitive cycle, demonstrating transfer of learned strategies to activities not directly practised. This indicates increased perceived self-efficacy, a central element in person-centred

OT [11,12]. As Levasseur et al. [16] noted, engagement in meaningful activities is a key determinant of well-being in people with chronic disability. Clinically, higher COPM scores and reduced PDQ-39 indices suggest a positive impact at both functional and psychological levels.

These outcomes occur within a complex condition characterized by progressive deterioration of motor and non-motor functions [2,3]; in this context, targeting occupational participation through cognitive strategies represents a valid and innovative therapeutic opportunity.

Another salient aspect was the centrality of the patient's active role, aligned with the client-centred stance of CO-OP [15,27]. Defining meaningful goals strengthened motivation and adherence—two key success factors in managing chronic conditions [5]. Allowing patients to autonomously select activities is a core CO-OP principle, enhancing engagement, motivation, and functional relevance of the intervention. In PD, choices such as cutting meat, screwing, or using technological devices reflect concrete needs and personal aims that can be addressed through targeted cognitive strategies. Cutting meat, for instance, involves fine motor control, bimanual coordination, and force modulation—skills often compromised in PD. Screwing requires motor planning, manual dexterity, and sequencing, whereas device use engages higher cognitive functions such as attention, working memory, and cognitive flexibility. CO-OP enables patients to develop personalized strategies to overcome difficulties in each activity, promoting self-efficacy and generalization of competencies in real-world, meaningful contexts.

This case further supports the crucial role of OT in PD, not only as functional support but as an intervention to promote participation and autonomy through personalized, person-centred approaches. Integrating cognitive strategies, as in CO-OP, fits coherently within OT's theoretical framework, which considers the individual holistically within their environment and meaningful activities.

Study limitations

Several limitations must be acknowledged. The descriptive, non-experimental nature of the study and the absence of specific tools to assess metacognition limit objective measurement of changes in relevant cognitive processes. In addition, the lack of long-term follow-up precludes verification of the stability of acquired skills. Future studies should include long-term follow-up assessments to better evaluate the persistence of functional gains and investigate the potential generalization of acquired strategies over time. Furthermore, larger sample sizes and controlled study designs are needed to strengthen the evidence base on CO-OP efficacy in Parkinson's disease. A

lthough caregivers were not formally involved in this case, the literature highlights their value in the rehabilitation process. Dutch guidelines [25] recommend active caregiver inclusion in OT pathways for people with PD. However, evidence on the effectiveness of therapy–caregiver interactions remains limited [26], indicating the need to develop OT approaches that also support the family network. Intervention success was also facilitated by the occupational therapist's active collaboration, which supported guided exploration, selection of meaningful goals, and construction of personal strategies. The professional played an educational role, fostering autonomy, strategic reflection, and self-efficacy—elements recognized in the literature as key facilitators of participation [12,13]. The observed results are consistent with Foster [5], who reported that OT interventions focused on instrumental ADL can improve participation in people with PD. Moreover, as highlighted in two studies [2,3], functional decline associated with disease progression can be countered through participation-oriented approaches. In this scenario, CO-OP may represent a preventive strategy to slow deterioration and improve QoL [27].

CONCLUSIONS

Application of the CO-OP model in this case produced positive rehabilitative outcomes, with substantial improvements in both occupational performance and perceived satisfaction for the selected meaningful activities. The

patient achieved greater autonomy in meal-time management—particularly functional handling of cutlery to cut meat independently; improved ability to screw screws of different sizes and resistances—reacquiring skills useful for minor repairs; and regained competencies for appropriate use of personal technological devices (smartphone and tablet). These activities had previously been disorganized or avoided. Internalization of the Goal–Plan–Do–Check metacognitive cycle enabled the patient not only to improve the treated activities but also to transfer strategic skills to domains not directly addressed during therapy, indicating genuine generalization.

This supports the effectiveness of CO-OP in degenerative neurological contexts and in adults, broadening its applicability beyond paediatric or post-acute settings. In summary, this case supports CO-OP as a personalized, effective, person-centred rehabilitation intervention capable of promoting participation, autonomy, and quality of life in people with Parkinson's disease. This approach benefits people with PD and their caregivers by fostering autonomy across domains. Finally, reducing stigma and stereotypes surrounding the disease—frequent drivers of social isolation and discrimination—is an important target for improving the QoL of those affected and those around them [29;30].

Future directions

It would be desirable to expand the evidence base through randomized controlled trials or case series involving more individuals with PD to verify replicability and strengthen evidence for CO-OP's effectiveness, also incorporating targeted psychometric measures (e.g., executive-function tests, metacognitive self-assessment) to better monitor cognitive changes related to the intervention. According to a recent study [28], it would also be advisable to begin replacing paper-and-pencil neuropsychological tests with digital formats, which yield better results in terms of efficiency, precision, and SUS scores.

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